

Synthesis and Mass Spectral Studies of Ketimines. Part-I. Fragmentation of some New α -(1,3-Dioxoindan-2-yl)ethylidene/arylideneanilines under Electron Impact

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Condensation of 2-acylindan-1,3-diones (1) with anilines afforded the corresponding anils (2a-j) which were characterised by elemental analyses and ir and pmr spectral data. Electron impact mass fragmentation of these anils is reported.

A perusal of literature reveals the mass spectral studies of a few aldimines¹⁻⁹. Fragmentation of ketimines does not seem to have been properly investigated. It was therefore thought worthwhile to study the mass spectra of ketimines, such as α -(1,3-dioxoindan-2-yl)ethylidene (2a-h) and similar benzylidene anilines (2i, j). These compounds were prepared by the condensation of 2-acylindan-1,3-diones (1) with anilines (Scheme 1; Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The mass spectra of the anils showed intense molecular ion peaks which also constituted the base peak (except the anil 2i which displayed the base peak at m/z 77 due to $C_8H_7^+$). Three important modes of fragmentation have been identified (Chart 1). All the anils showed sequential losses of CH_3 and CN radicals generating ions 4 ($M-15$)⁺ and 5 ($M-41$)⁺, respectively. The latter ions could also arise through direct loss of CH_3CN from molecular ion, since Schiff bases derived from 2-formylpyridine and isopropylamine are known to lose CH_3CN in a similar fashion⁶. A noteworthy feature is that the relative intensity of ($M-41$)⁺ ions increases with electron-donating substituents and decreases with electron-withdrawing ones. In

Scheme 1

case of halogenated anils, the relative abundance decreases with decrease in electronegativity of the

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (2a-j)

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹	δ (ppm)
2a	145	72	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	1 695 (C=O), 1 690 (C=N)	2.60 (3H, s, CH ₃ C=N), 7.70-7.90 (9H, m, ArH), 12.80 (1H, br, enolif)
2b	140	74	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	1 690, 1 690	2.98 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 2.60 (3H, s, CH ₃ C=N), 7.15 (2H, d, H-2', H-6'), 7.25 (2H, d, H-3', H-5'), 7.50-7.80 (4H, m, ArH)
2c	160	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	1 675, 1 690	2.70 (3H, s, CH ₃), 4.00 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 7.25-7.90 (8H, m, ArH)
2d	170	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCl	1 690, 1 690	2.72 (3H, s, CH ₃), 7.28-7.90 (8H, m, ArH)

2j, ions 7 and 8 corresponding to both the losses of OH radical ($M-17$)⁺ and H₂O ($M-18$)⁺ from their respective molecular ions have been noticed. The latter ions lose HCN generating respective ions (9) at m/z 280 and 294 (Chart 1).

The anils (2a-h) exhibit imine-enamine tautomerism and fragmentation of the enamine form predominates leading to the formation of the aromatic amine radical ion (15) and another ion (13) at m/z 170; it may be considered to arise through the participation of the α -methyl group, as the anils bearing a phenyl group (2i, j) did not produce ions 10, 11 and 13 at m/z 172, 171 and 170, respectively. Another distinguishing feature is that the ion at m/z 172 fragments further generate ions 12 (m/z 115) and 14 (m/z 89).

Experimental

Melting points were measured in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer and mass spectra on a MS-12 mass spectrometer operating at 70 eV.

Preparation of ketimines (2a-j): A mixture of equimolar amounts of 2-acyl- or 2-aroylindan-1,3-diones (1a-j; 0.01 mol) and anilines (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to afford yellow green needles of 2a-j (Table 1).

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